

Kaiser, K.A., Urberg, M., Johnsson, M., Kemp, J., Meadows, A., Paglione, L. (2021) An International, Multi-Stakeholder Survey about Metadata Awareness, Knowledge and Use in Scholarly Communications. Quantitative Science Studies. Advance Publication. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00133

**An International, Multi-Stakeholder Survey about Metadata
Awareness, Knowledge, and Use in Scholarly Communications**

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Peer Review: https://publons.com/publons/10.1162/qss_a_00133

20 **Abstract**

21 The Metadata 2020 initiative is an ongoing effort to bring various scholarly communications
22 stakeholder groups together to promote principles and standards of practice to improve the
23 quality of metadata. To understand the perspectives and practices regarding metadata of the
24 main stakeholder groups (librarians, publishers, researchers and repository managers), we
25 conducted a survey during summer 2019. The survey content was generated by
26 representatives from the stakeholder groups.

27 A link to an online survey (17 or 18 questions depending on the group) was
28 distributed through multiple social media, listserv, and blog outlets. Responses were
29 anonymous, with an optional entry for names and email addresses for those who were willing
30 to be contacted later. Complete responses (N=211; 87 librarians, 27 publishers, 48 repository
31 managers, and 49 researchers) representing 23 countries on four continents were analyzed
32 and summarized for thematic content and ranking of awareness and practices.

33 Across the stakeholder groups, the level of awareness and usage of metadata methods
34 and practices was highly variable. Clear gaps across the groups point to the need for
35 consolidation of schema and practices, as well as broad educational efforts in order to
36 increase knowledge and implementation of metadata in scholarly communications.

37 **Keywords:** metadata, standards, workflows, interoperability, researchers, FAIR
38 principles

1. An International, Multi-Stakeholder Survey about Metadata

Awareness, Knowledge, and Use in Scholarly Communications

Classifying and/or descriptive information about knowledge resources (what we now call metadata) has been in existence as long as libraries have. Callimachus of Cyrene created the Pinakes ([Jones 2015](#)), often characterized as the first library catalog, and serving a collection of bibliographic (meta)data about each of the works in the Library of Alexandria in 245 BCE. With the event of computers, Stuart McIntosh and David Griffel created a system called ADMINS ([McIntosh 1967](#)) in the 1960s that created a similar cataloging resource to that of the Pinakes, lists of the library contents from several points of view (by author, by subject, etc.). However, they instead codified this information by attaching a set of “meta data” to the resources themselves, and then using a computer system to produce a list of resources from the desired point of view. As metadata became incorporated into various scholarly communications systems (publishing, data repositories, cataloging, etc.), it maintained status as a characteristic of the resources and systems themselves, often optimized for the use of the organization or system codifying the metadata rather than for the consumers of this information. A consequence of this evolution is that metadata maintenance and distribution hasn’t really evolved as an industry of its own. Instead, it relies on sets of disparate standards and loose agreements for metadata exchange, leaving some of the more ambitious promises of metadata unfulfilled as a mechanism for discovery, innovation and knowledge distribution as individual stakeholders understandably invest resources to optimize metadata use to address their own needs and goals.

60 **1.1 Previous work that informs this project**

61 In 2019, the participants of the Metadata 2020 initiative published a review that
62 examined the published literature regarding the use of metadata in scholarly communications
63 ([Gregg 2019](#)). The aim of this literature review was to address “...a need for a comprehensive
64 review of the challenges, opportunities, and gaps with metadata in scholarly communications
65 with the aim that it would foster further conversations among the stakeholders involved.”
66 ([Gregg 2019](#)) Many challenges, gaps and opportunities were revealed. This survey project
67 follows the review’s structure, asking questions of similar stakeholder groups to gain
68 additional insights into metadata knowledge, use, standards, practices and other factors that
69 not only describe the present landscape, but point to potentially other opportunities to
70 improve industry practices.

71 Another project of Metadata 2020 participants’ work was focused on developing
72 personas for those involved in metadata work, based on their metadata roles rather than their
73 job titles or organization type — metadata creators, curators, custodians, and consumers.
74 ([Metadata 2020 Personas 2020](#)) Metadata creators provide descriptive information
75 (metadata) about research and scholarly outputs; curators classify, normalize, and standardize
76 this descriptive information to increase its value as a resource; custodians store and maintain
77 this descriptive information and make it available for consumers; and consumers knowingly
78 or unknowingly use the descriptive information to find, discover, connect, and cite research
79 and scholarly outputs. In analyzing the survey responses, the benefits of this approach
80 become apparent in addressing metadata challenges. We consider the application of a
81 persona approach in our discussion and concluding remarks.

82 **1.2 About the present work**

83 The survey provides insights from four key stakeholder groups for the metadata
84 associated with scholarly objects — researchers, librarians, repository managers, and
85 publishers. Respondents to the survey hailed from four continents (23 countries) and
86 represented individuals from all stages of their careers. Additional details about respondents
87 can be found in the methods section (section 2). This paper shares the survey results and our
88 insights organized by stakeholder group, mapped against their persona(s). De-identified, raw
89 data; detailed survey result summaries; and the original survey questions are made available
90 for further study by the reader. Details on accessing these resources can be found in [section](#)
91 [6. Supplementary Materials](#).

92 **1.3 About the Metadata 2020 Initiative**

93 Initiated by a diverse group of volunteers in 2017 ([About Metadata 2020](#)), Metadata
94 2020 expanded quickly to develop into an international community of stakeholders from
95 across scholarly communications. It functions as a collaboration advocating for "richer,
96 connected and reusable, open metadata for all research outputs in order to advance scholarly
97 pursuits for the benefit of society." ([About Metadata 2020](#)) While many efforts have been
98 made to address challenges in single communities, few have extended solutions that are
99 targeted to be applied across them. Recognizing this situation as a strength, the Metadata
100 2020 conveners agreed on an agenda driven by the interests and needs of this broad
101 community. This approach allowed for unrestricted interactions among the subgroups
102 participating in Metadata 2020 as determined by its volunteer community members and
103 needs for additional expertise and review. As part of this initiative, in order to better

104 understand how and the degree to which various stakeholders in scholarly communications
105 understand and use metadata, and using insights gained from the aforementioned literature
106 review, we deemed it necessary to test our personal impressions with a broader audience in
107 the form of a survey. The survey was conducted by a sub-group called Research
108 Communication within the project Metadata 2020.

109 **2. Methods**

110 Questionnaire content by stakeholder groups (librarians, publishers, repository
111 managers, and researchers) was drafted by the first author first for researchers, and then
112 circulated to other project teams in the Metadata 2020 community to customize the questions
113 for the other stakeholder groups. More specialized selection lists or modifications to
114 questions were done by Metadata 2020 team members who identified with that stakeholder
115 group and posted for review and comment. Final versions of question sets for the four
116 stakeholder groups were then harmonized to allow for cross-stakeholder answer
117 comparisons. An online survey tool (SurveyGizmo, Boulder, Colorado, USA) was used to
118 create the question sets and branching structure based on the roles of stakeholders. The
119 questions and answer choices were presented in English. The survey was released for public
120 participation on June 5, 2019 and closed Monday, July 15, 2019. Participants were recruited
121 via direct emails of personal contacts, social media (Twitter, Facebook), blogs (e.g., *The*
122 *Scholarly Kitchen*, listservs, and online newsletters). The questions and response options may
123 be found in [Section 6. Supplementary Materials](#). The first author summarized and analyzed
124 all data, with input from stakeholder group members on creating categories of job roles/titles.
125 All authors reviewed the analysis and raw data and discussed how to compare within and

126 between the groups. The survey questions and protocol for data collection and handling were
127 reviewed by the University of Alabama at Birmingham Institutional Review Board.

128 3. Analysis

129 A total of 222 submitted responses were received and organized in Microsoft Excel™
130 (Redmond, WA, USA) by the first author. Responses were evaluated for completeness, and
131 any (n=11) that were mostly blank responses were not further analyzed. The analyzed set
132 total was 211 respondents.

133 Complete responses among the four stakeholder groups consisted of:

- 134 ● 87 librarians,
- 135 ● 27 publishers,
- 136 ● 48 repository managers, and
- 137 ● 49 researchers.

138 Overall, the sample consisted of respondents from four continents, from which 23
139 countries were represented (Table 1). Sixty-four respondents voluntarily provided their
140 names and contact information to clarify free responses to questions as needed.

141 **Table 1**

142 *Survey Respondents by Country and Stakeholder Group*

# Respondents	Librarian	Publisher	Repository Manager	Researcher	Grand Total	% Total
United States	48	14	22	10	94	45%
United Kingdom	18	6	12	9	45	21%
Canada	6	1	1	5	13	6%
Australia	3	1	7	2	13	6%
Germany	2	2	4	3	11	5%
Sweden	6			3	9	4%

# Respondents	Librarian	Publisher	Repository Manager	Researcher	Grand Total	% Total
Netherlands	1	1	1	2	5	2%
France			1	2	3	1%
India		1		1	2	1%
Italy				2	2	1%
Saudi Arabia				1	1	<1%
Brazil		1			1	<1%
Botswana				1	1	<1%
Anonymous				1	1	<1%
Venezuela				1	1	<1%
Malaysia				1	1	<1%
Serbia				1	1	<1%
Croatia				1	1	<1%
Switzerland				1	1	<1%
Nigeria				1	1	<1%
Ghana	1				1	<1%
Norway	1				1	<1%
Austria	1				1	<1%
Portugal				1	1	<1%
Grand Total	87	27	48	49	211	

143

144 Since the question sets were specific to each target stakeholder group, each group’s
 145 data is summarized separately. Where possible and with care to avoid risk of losing meaning,
 146 free responses were coded into categories to aid in identification of themes or classes of
 147 responses by Metadata 2020 team members who were part of the respective stakeholder
 148 groups. *Note.* Numbers reported in the results section in each stakeholder response set may
 149 not add up to the group total when a response may have covered more than one category, or
 150 some items were not selected.

151 The author team viewed the data for summary insights based on the questions in three
 152 perspectives:

- 153 ● Information about the respondent and who this person interacts with in terms of
- 154 metadata used or workflows
- 155 ● Information about how this person interacts with metadata from internal or
- 156 external sources
- 157 ● Metadata specifics

158 All survey questions as well as visualized raw responses and coded interpretations are
159 available in [section 6. Supplementary Materials](#).

160 4. Summarized Results

161 4.1 Librarians

162 4.1.1 About Librarian Respondents

163 The highest response rate of the survey was from the librarians group. Most librarians
164 (n=87) responded via the direct email, and 47 % were from the United States, 18% from the
165 United Kingdom, 6% from Canada, 6% from Sweden. The concept of “metadata” is highly
166 central and well-known in the library sector — librarians are primarily curators, custodians,
167 and consumers of metadata — so the comparatively high engagement and interest of this
168 group was not surprising. Moreover, research on metadata for scholarly communications is
169 quite dominated by the library and information sector, which was also reflected in the
170 literature review by Gregg, et al. ([Gregg 2019](#)).

171 The respondents were asked to describe in free text their roles and subject areas, and
172 there were a variety of responses to this question. The responses were grouped into 4 areas of
173 common roles for library services with a fifth category of miscellaneous ‘other’ roles. Most

174 respondents have roles related to “Cataloging and metadata”. See Figure 1 below for the

175 relative distribution of roles for Librarian respondents.

176 **Figure 1**

177 *Library/ Information Science Specialty or Subject Area*

Library/ information science speciality or subject area

Summarized and grouped answers

178

179 *Note.* Write-in answers have been summarized and grouped into broader categories.

180 Generally, most of the respondents come from very traditional libraries with the
181 common offering of services. This is also reflected in the results of the remaining questions,
182 available in [section 6. Supplementary Materials](#).

183 **4.1.2 Library Insights**

184 Librarians focus on offering researcher education about metadata in different ways
185 (Library Survey Q4). While the question was posed requesting a free-text answer, offerings
186 for metadata education and support could be grouped into several broad categories:

- 187 ● Group: Classes and workshops (34.9%, n=44)

- 188 ● Personalized or Individual: Individual services and consulting (30.2%, n=38)
- 189 ● Self-Serve: Web-based user guides and software tools (14.3%, n=18)
- 190 ● Enhancement to Research Assets (8.7%, n=11)

191 However, supporting and educating research is only a component of librarian
192 activities. When asked about the role of their services and support of metadata (Library
193 Survey Q5), creating and analyzing cataloging metadata is a slightly more common role:

- 194 ● Create/analyze cataloging metadata (29.2%, n=21)
- 195 ● Support researchers with metadata production (22.2%, n=16)
- 196 ● Create institutional repository metadata (13.9%, n=10)
- 197 ● Assist with discovery of research (9.7%, n=7)

198 Responses to these two questions, moreover, revealed a strong correlation between
199 description of metadata support methods--education vs. enhancements--and the job title
200 identified in Library Survey (Library Survey Q2). For example, catalogers and metadata
201 librarians focus on creating enhancements with bibliographic records, while reference
202 librarians tend to focus on education through group instruction, individual consults, and self-
203 serve library guides.

204 Researchers' interactions with librarians were revealed to be targeted interactions
205 about planning research projects (48%), including asking for help finding scholarship and
206 data sets, and about post-project publication and reporting help (47%) (Library Survey Q7).
207 When researchers seek consulting services about where to find scholarship or datasets,
208 librarians point them toward services that support rich, accurate, and elaborated metadata:
209 first to Abstracting/Indexing Databases (59.8%), then to Discovery layer keyword searches

210 (46%) and to Discovery layer subject searches (41.4%) (Library Survey Q8). When librarians
211 discuss searching strategies with patrons, they report Title (53%), Year and Date of
212 Publication (44%) and Author name(s) (44%) as the three most important pieces of
213 information to finding relevant scholarship or datasets (Library Survey Q12). These three
214 fields correspond with the three fields librarians identify as most important in scholarly
215 publication (Library Survey Q11). Librarians also report that researchers often do not ask
216 directly about metadata, rather they ask questions *related to metadata* in some way (n=54).
217 When researchers do specifically inquire about metadata, they often want to learn *how to*
218 *create metadata* (41%) (Library Survey Q9).

219 **4.1.3 Key Librarian Themes**

220 The responses indicated that librarians have a strong motivation to instruct and
221 educate users about metadata and are highly engaged with maintaining good metadata
222 records in systems – as they understand metadata’s importance for knowledge discovery and
223 scholarly communication. Responses show that:

- 224 ● Many librarians are educating and instructing users about metadata through
225 classes and workshops, by individual consulting and by web-based user-guides.
- 226 ● Quality control of metadata in various systems is a major and time-consuming
227 task for many librarians.
- 228 ● Librarian metadata work is spread across multiple systems including in library
229 catalogs and discovery layers for item-level cataloguing or in Current Research
230 Information Systems (CRIS) systems or other repositories where they check
231 researchers’ publications

- 232 • Metadata is important. “...we aim to ensure that metadata is fit for purpose, well
233 maintained and widely disseminated” – one of many statements indicating the
234 importance of metadata according to librarians.

235 In several previous publications, authors discuss the problems libraries experience
236 with poor and/or incomplete metadata received from publishers and system vendors, and the
237 needs and opportunities for collaboration between these groups ([Poole 2016](#), [Kemp 2018](#),
238 [Bascones 2018](#), [Flynn 2013](#)).

239 **4.2 Publishers**

240 **4.2.1 About Publisher Respondents**

241 Surprisingly, although publishers may be metadata creators, curators, custodians, and
242 consumers, they were least well represented in the survey results, with just 27 completed
243 responses. Most respondents were US-based (52%, n=14) or UK-based (22%, n=6), with the
244 remainder of respondents coming from six other countries. The most well represented job
245 functions among respondents were editors (30.8%, n=8) and/or director-level strategic
246 managers (23.2%, n=6), including two of the production/content management respondents,
247 perhaps indicating an understanding of how better metadata will help increase their
248 organization’s success in the future. Other job functions represented included content
249 management, data management, and information discovery/library support (Publisher Survey
250 Q2). Despite the low response rate from publishers in this survey, previous research shows
251 that publishers are engaged in improving their metadata and willing to invest in new
252 technologies to process it ([Gregg 2019](#), [Imbue Partners 2017](#), [Kemp 2018](#)).

253 **4.2.2 Publishing Insights**

254 Nearly half of respondents (48.5%, n=16) either felt that there was little or no support
255 for metadata education of users by their organizations, or they were unclear about the level of
256 support (Publisher Survey Q3). Likewise, about half of respondents (48%, n=13) felt that the
257 critical issues with metadata for their publications reside with the researchers - and yet
258 educating researchers does not seem to be a priority most of the respondents (Publisher
259 Survey Q9). A significant number of respondents (34.5%, n=10) did not know what changes,
260 if any, should be made to their organization's approach to metadata education for end users
261 (Publisher Survey Q4).

262 Lack of controlled metadata is seen as a problem by many respondents. It was ranked
263 the second most critical issue in workflows (48%) (Publisher Survey Q9), and related issues
264 such as the need for standardization and consistency, were mentioned several times in free
265 text comments identifying critical issues for metadata submission (Publisher Survey Q6).
266 Exacerbating this problem, metadata was identified to be entered at least partly manually in
267 most organizations represented, either by internal experts (70%), authors (59%), or external
268 experts (26%) (Publisher Survey Q5). It may also explain why publisher respondents ranked
269 internal cleanup lower than the lack of controlled metadata as a critical issue (Publisher
270 Survey Q8). Over half of publishers reported a combination of manual and automatic
271 metadata workflows, but only four reported use of automated processes exclusively
272 (Publisher's Survey Q5). As shown in Figure 2, when scholarly publishers export their
273 metadata, it can be found in many places, particularly Crossref ([Crossref 2020](#)), library
274 service platforms, aggregators and PubMed ([PubMed 2020](#)) (Publisher Survey Q8).

275 **Figure 2**

276 *Metadata Destination When Exported*

Metadata destination when exported

% respondents that selected location. Multiple answers encouraged.

277

278 *Note.* Figure shows the percentage of respondents that selected the destination. Multiple
279 answers were encouraged.

280 There was clear consensus about the most important metadata elements, with (in
281 order) title (93%), year and date of publication, DOI (each 89%), author name/s (81%), and
282 abstract (70%) noticeably more highly ranked than any of the other options (Publisher
283 Survey Q11). Unsurprisingly, most of these were also the top elements respondents said were
284 required in internal publisher systems and their content platforms, though abstracts were
285 ranked slightly lower and, instead, volume and issue number were seen as more important
286 (Publisher Survey Q12). The NISO JATS schema ([Journal Article Tag Suite, 2020](#)) was by
287 far the most used metadata schema used by publishers (63%) (Publisher Survey Q14).

288 **4.2.3 Key Publisher Themes**

289 Through their interactions with researchers as both creators and consumers of content,
290 publishers are well placed to play a stronger role in improving metadata workflows than they
291 appear to do currently based on the responses to this survey. For example:

- 292 ● **Communication Need-Priority Mismatch.** Publisher respondents saw lack of
293 understanding of the benefits of metadata for end users (59%) and for discovery
294 (70%) as the most critical issues for authors (Publisher Survey Q6), although de-
295 emphasized promotion and guidance as an area for education support (20.7%,
296 n=6) (Publisher Survey Q4). Where support was provided by publishers, it was as
297 a mix of e-resources (18.2%, n=6) and live resources (21.2%, n=7). Others
298 indicated support though did not specify the type (12.1%, n=4) (Publisher Survey
299 Q3). Most respondents (34.5%) had no suggestions for changing the support they
300 provide. Of those that suggested changes, most favored promoting its benefits
301 (20.7%), providing technical support (17.2%), or providing guidelines and
302 templates (13.8%). (Publisher Survey Q4)
- 303 ● **Limited Support for Author-Driven Metadata Correction.** The publisher
304 respondents report limited or no opportunities for authors to update their own
305 metadata after submitting it. Only one respondent indicated that their organization
306 allows authors to update all fields themselves (Publisher Survey Q7). Where
307 metadata can be updated this appears to be a manual or publisher-controlled
308 process that would be seen as a barrier by researchers, or a sign that publishers do

309 not value their input on metadata creation or curation for their own works. If
310 authors are to take ownership of their metadata, this clearly needs to be addressed.
311 • **Inconsistent Quality Verification Methods.** Because of wide variability in
312 quality methods, metadata quality and completeness are likely to vary widely.
313 Data entry is done manually (at least in part) by most respondents, either by
314 internal experts (70%) or by authors (59%). (Publisher Survey Q5) Over half of
315 respondents have some sort of automated metadata checking process in place
316 (59%), but most also use other manual forms of checking — either in their own
317 systems (48%) or other systems (33%), or via curated support from others (44%),
318 with 11% reporting no checking at all (Publisher Survey Q10).

319 4.3 Repository Managers

320 4.3.1 About Repository Manager Respondents

321 The repository managers group has the most diverse set roles within the groups
322 surveyed. Some respondents are in charge of units, divisions, or organizations that manage
323 data in repositories (e.g., managers, directors, head); some are working directly with data
324 ingestion or manipulation (e.g., analyst, curator, archivist); some are helping researchers use
325 a repository effectively or to plan for managing their data and scholarship in a repository
326 (e.g., research data librarian, digital collections librarian); many work in a variety of contexts
327 within the same organization. These respondents work with a wide variety of data types, with
328 a variety of workflows, and manage their metadata using many different standards.

329 Repository managers are typically curators and custodians of metadata. The
330 professional duties of this group vary widely, with most working in a university setting (73%,

331 n=35), and others in an industry setting (21%, n=10), or public archival role (6%, n=3)
332 (Repository Manager Survey Q2). Of the 48 responses received, nearly half work in the
333 United States (45%, n=22), a quarter work in the United Kingdom (25%, n=12), fewer work
334 in Australia (15%, n=7), and the remainder work in Germany or Canada or France or the
335 Netherlands (15%, n=7).

336 4.3.2 Repository Metadata Insights

337 Most organizations--university or industry--use a combination of manual and
338 automatic methods to create data in their system about repository content (Repository
339 Manager Survey Q7, Figure 3). Several respondents indicated other methods (38%), for
340 example, using CRIS, Symplectic Elements or ETDs (Electronic Theses and Dissertations) to
341 harvest metadata, which is then used in conjunction with manual repository workflows.

342 Figure 3

343 *Methods of data entry into repository systems*

344
345 *Note.* Figure shows the percentage of respondents that selected the method.

346 Half of the respondents identified two or three workflow challenges (50%, n=24). The
347 top three challenge areas identified by this group are associated with the researcher (80%),

348 internal data clean up (58%) and lack of controlled vocabulary (46%) (Repository Manager
349 Survey Q11).

350 Most of the repositories not only ingest metadata but export it as well. DataCite
351 ([DataCite 2020](#)) (50%) and Library Service Platforms (44%) were the two most commonly
352 reported places to deposit repository data (Repository Manager Q9). Unexpected was the
353 wide variety of options not included in the survey (other, 44%). The written in responses
354 revealed that repositories deposit their data into a very different set of tools than librarians or
355 publishers. Google Scholar, CORE, and Trove were common tools for this group not
356 originally identified in the survey options. The evolution of institutional repositories as well
357 as discipline-based repositories for research data have been discussed a lot in the literature
358 recently ([Gregg 2019](#)). Many organizations with institutional repositories have spent a lot of
359 resources reviewing their workflows for populating their repositories with data and metadata
360 ([Jennings 2017](#), [Bull 2016](#)). The expansion of repositories has also to do with the intensive
361 development of open data and research data management during the last years ([Kratz 2015](#),
362 [Leonelli 2016](#), [Harvey 2017](#)).

363 Most of the repositories require metadata to be present at the time of deposit (77%),
364 which aligns with what repository managers hear from their clients and patrons about their
365 challenges with entering data (Repository Manager Survey Q10). The top three critical issues
366 identified by the repository managers for those entering data in their system are the time
367 needed to add required information (67%); lack of knowledge about the impact of metadata
368 in discovery (65%); and frustrations about manual entry for different types of research
369 objects (60%) (Repository Manager Survey Q8, Figure 4).

370 **Figure 4**

371 *Critical issues for metadata submitters*

Critical issues for metadata submitters

% Respondents selecting the issue. Multiple answers encouraged

372

373 *Note.* Figure shows the percentage of respondents selecting the issue. Multiple answers were
374 encouraged.

375 The standards, schema, specifications, and element sets used by this group vary
376 widely, and many repositories use at least one other standard for recording metadata about
377 their repository objects. Dublin Core (DC) is the most-used element set (49%), with DataCite
378 XML (19%) and MODS (17%) used third and fourth-most. The wide use of Dublin Core is
379 not surprising given that many of the respondents are embedded in a university setting. The
380 Other category (second, 33%) also revealed a weakness in the survey instrument: DDI, ISO
381 9115, and internal schema should have been included. As one respondent points out, the
382 answer options for this question were very library [and publisher] centric. (Repository
383 Manager Survey Q15)

384 The pieces of metadata identified by repository managers as being “required”
385 (Repository Manager Survey Q13) versus “most important” (Repository Manager Survey
386 Q14) reveal a couple of telling pieces of information. Direct Object Identifiers (DOIs) are
387 identified as the fourth most important pieces of metadata (65%) behind Title, Author
388 Name(s), and Year and Date of Publication, but they are ninth most important in the
389 metadata required for deposit (40%). Author ORCIDs ([ORCID 2020](https://orcid.org/)), likewise were
390 identified as the sixth most important piece of metadata (46%), but ORCIDs do not appear in
391 the top ten required pieces of metadata.

392 ***4.3.3 Key Repository Manager Themes***

393 A high-level analysis of the responses reveals a few key things about repository
394 managers:

- 395 ● Repositories are found in a lot of different corners of the scholarly
396 communications life cycle and no two repositories are alike
- 397 ● They have a number of different metadata needs with respect to what pieces of
398 content are necessary and important for a repository to record and make
399 accessible deposited content.
- 400 ● Content intervention by humans is still required in repositories to address gaps in
401 controlled vocabularies, but opportunities exist for automation to assist content
402 and metadata ingestion.

403 **4.4 Researchers**

404 **4.4.1 About Researcher Respondents**

405 Researchers are primarily creators and consumers of metadata (e.g., keywords for
406 articles, dataset descriptions). However, they reported very little knowledge about broader
407 types of metadata (n=49 respondents). Since the survey was short and simple, we can only
408 speculate as to whether researchers may be motivated to learn more or do more to support
409 better metadata for creation and curation of research outputs that support their own needs.
410 Researchers need to be educated in ways that creation of richer metadata will enhance the
411 utility of the scientific record, including supporting findability and potentially increasing
412 citations (a metric important to many researchers).

413 Most researchers responded via email distribution links, and the top three countries
414 represented by respondents were the United States (20%), the United Kingdom (18%), and
415 Canada (10%). The researchers reported specific fields of study or research, which were then
416 more generally categorized. (Researcher Study Q2, Figure 5)

417 **Figure 5**

418 *Researcher's Field and/or Topic*

Research field and/or topic

Summarized and grouped answers

419

420 *Note.* Write-in answers have been summarized and grouped into broader categories.4.4.2

421 **Research Insights**

422 Respondents reported 94% actively publishing their research (Researcher Study Q4),
423 and 91% reported collaborating with other researchers (Researcher Study Q5). When asked
424 about their concept of metadata (when you think of the term “metadata” what comes to
425 mind?), their free-text responses (summarized in Figure 6) reflected the wide variety of
426 experiences, uses, and understanding about metadata among researchers (Researcher Survey
427 Q6).

428 **Figure 6**

429 *Categorized conceptions of metadata among researcher respondents*

What comes to mind when you hear the term "metadata"?

Summarized and interpreted answers.

430

431 When asked about the most important pieces of information about research objects in
432 order to make them accessible and useful to others in their field in future, the top five
433 selected responses were title (90%), author name (90%), date of publication (86%), digital
434 object identifier (DOI - 72%), and abstract (56%) (Researcher Survey Q8). When asked what
435 pieces of information are most helpful in finding articles sought, the top five selected
436 responses were title (88%), author name (70%), abstract (54%), publication date (50%), and
437 DOI (36%) (Researcher Study Q9).

438 When seeing an interesting title or scanning through a table of contents, researchers
439 most indicated the following information as most important when deciding to read an article
440 or a book chapter in detail: full text access (86%), date published (44%), population and
441 design details (42%), availability in an online format (33%), and the authority of the authors
442 (32%) (Researcher Survey Q11).

443 Researchers indicated what they feel to be the most critical evidence and artifacts to
444 know to evaluate credibility and usefulness of a data set. The top information selected
445 include the collection creation description (72%), scope of the sample set (48%), limitations
446 of scope (48%), number of study subjects (44%), and use description (40%) (Researcher
447 Study Q12). Related to this evaluation, the following aspects were in the top five traits that
448 might prevent use of a dataset or piece of evidence, usage restrictions (56%), limitations of
449 scope (44%), financial costs (38%), file formats (30%), and collection creation process
450 (26%) (Researcher Study Q13).

451 Researchers were asked where they store data sets and other scholarly artifacts when
452 done using them. Many store them on their personal computer (64%), though for many, this
453 information is also stored elsewhere. just over half reported storing artifacts in institutional
454 storage (52%). Other locations include personal cloud storage (38%) and public repositories
455 or websites (36%) (Researcher Survey Q14).

456 There was not a high degree of consensus among the surveyed researchers about the
457 standardized metadata schemas that they use when publishing research outputs. About a third
458 of respondents indicated that they didn't know what standards were used (32%), and nearly
459 as many indicated that they use none of the schema (28%) or something other than the
460 choices provided (22%). The most popular schema from which they could select were Dublin
461 Core (22%), other (22%), and JATS (Journal Article Tagging Suite - 10%).

462 ***4.4.3 Key Researcher Themes***

463 Several key themes emerged about researchers:

- 464 ● The response patterns reflect a limited perspective of researchers as consumers of
465 metadata, or specific awareness or expressed needs about metadata for other
466 researcher purposes.
- 467 ● The reported common uses of metadata reflect the position of researcher as a
468 creator of content, but mostly for human consumption in small volumes rather
469 than for machine readability or large volume work.
- 470 ● Full access rights and information about usage restrictions is top of mind for
471 researchers. Although few questions asked about this directly, free-text and
472 provided comments frequently mentioned these topics.

473 **4.5 Cross-stakeholder insights**

474 All stakeholder groups were asked which metadata fields they feel are most
475 important, and which metadata schemas they use. These questions highlighted stark
476 differences between and--particularly in the case of repository managers--within each
477 stakeholder group.

478 ***4.5.1 Most important metadata fields: Different priorities across stakeholders***

479 Respondents were provided a list of 28 metadata fields commonly found in scholarly
480 publishing and were asked to select the set of them that they felt were the “most important.”
481 (Cross- Stakeholder A1) The list of fields was developed during a cross-stakeholder
482 workshop that listed the metadata fields that were most important to the participants. On
483 average, publishers selected more fields (11.4 on average) than the other stakeholders, and
484 nearly 40% more fields than librarians who on average selected 6.8 of the fields listed.
485 (Cross-Stakeholder A2)

486 **4.5.2 Metadata fields more important to publishers than other stakeholder groups**

487 In addition to selecting more fields, publishers were significantly MORE likely to
 488 select 11 specific fields than other stakeholders, particularly librarians. (Cross-Stakeholder
 489 A3)

490 **Table 2**

491 *Percentage of Respondents Indicating that a Metadata Field is Important, Compared to*
 492 *Publisher Responses*

Field	Publishers	Librarians		Repository		Researchers	
	%	%	Difference from Publishers	%	Difference from Publishers	%	Difference from Publishers
Yr. & date of pub	89%	57%	-32%	69%	-20%	86%	-3%
DOI	89%	47%	-43%	63%	-26%	72%	-17%
Abstract	71%	25%	-46%	43%	-29%	56%	-15%
Author(s) ORCID	54%	23%	-31%	45%	-9%	48%	-6%
Volume / issue	46%	27%	-19%	20%	-26%	34%	-12%
Author(s) affiliation	50%	10%	-40%	37%	-13%	30%	-20%
ISSN	43%	18%	-25%	27%	-16%	30%	-13%
Page numbers	39%	15%	-25%	16%	-23%	24%	-15%
Grant ID(s)	36%	8%	-28%	37%	1%	10%	-26%
Funder Name(s)	36%	9%	-27%	22%	-13%	18%	-18%
Funder ID(s)	32%	6%	-26%	24%	-13%	16%	-18%

493

494 *NOTE.* Publishers are more likely to select certain metadata fields as important compared to
 495 other stakeholder groups. Differences greater 20% are highlighted.

496 **4.5.3 Metadata fields significantly different in importance to librarians**

497 The fields that librarians selected as most important also varied significantly from
 498 other stakeholder groups, with librarians selecting several fields as important significantly
 499 LESS often than other stakeholder groups. Differences highlighted in red indicate metadata
 500 fields where librarians were less likely to indicate that the field was important. Highlighted in
 501 blue, the librarian group was more likely to indicate the field was important. (Cross-
 502 Stakeholder A4)

503 **Table 3**

504 *Percentage of Respondents Indicating that a Metadata Field is Important, Compared to*
 505 *Librarian Responses*

Field	Librarians	Publishers		Repository		Researchers	
	%	%	Difference from Librarians	%	Difference from Librarians	%	Difference from Librarians
Yr. & date of pub	57%	89%	32%	69%	13%	86%	29%
DOI	47%	89%	43%	63%	17%	72%	25%
Abstract	25%	71%	46%	43%	18%	56%	31%
Author(s) ORCID	23%	54%	31%	45%	22%	48%	25%
Volume / issue	27%	46%	19%	20%	-7%	34%	7%
Author(s) affiliation	10%	50%	40%	37%	27%	30%	20%
Grant ID(s)	8%	36%	28%	37%	29%	10%	2%
Language of content	26%	21%	-5%	22%	-4%	20%	-6%
Local controlled subject vocab	20%	25%	5%	24%	4%	10%	-10%
LCSH subjects	28%	11%	-18%	2%	-26%	6%	-22%
MeSH Subjects	14%	18%	4%	2%	-12%	10%	-4%

506

507 *Note.* Metadata fields that are significantly different in importance to librarians.

508 % Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged. > 20% difference is

509 highlighted.

510 **5. Discussion and Recommendations**

511 **5.1 Metadata now and then – the view of metadata throughout the years**

512 Libraries have dominated the application and development of modern metadata and
513 systems for cataloging metadata, since before the adoption of the Dewey Decimal
514 Classification in 1876 and the Universal Decimal Classification in 1895 and continue to drive
515 adoption of new standards and best practices for a wide variety of content types. Publishers
516 have long needed supply chain metadata to help them sell their content, but this metadata has
517 traditionally been proprietary and not interoperable. Repositories are not streamlined either
518 and lack a systematic approach to metadata creation, though Dublin Core Metadata may be
519 the most common schema to follow. Researchers have, more or less, been guided in their
520 creation of metadata by the other three groups and need to collaborate with the other three
521 groups in order to create research documentation and create metadata for access and
522 discovery.

523 For all of these stakeholders in the scholarly communications lifecycle, metadata
524 processes rely on heavily manual or semi-manual processes for creation and dissemination of
525 metadata. No single powerful best practice or standard or software system drives the
526 metadata ecosystem. The environment reflects a fragmented and organic growth that was
527 originally designed around print-based workflows. Workflows for metadata do not always
528 produce desired discovery; unclear ownership over metadata creation can lead to gaps in

529 coverage; very few fields are consistently required or used for discovery, challenging the
530 promises often made about metadata. In many cases, answers in this survey reflect the
531 haphazard development of systems creating and using metadata; nevertheless, several issues
532 are common to all stakeholder groups who replied to the survey. Everyone reported problems
533 with the large amount of time needed for submitting metadata, inadequate knowledge about
534 the impact of metadata for discovery, and frustration about manual entry of metadata into
535 repositories, catalogs, and publication systems.

536 **5.2 Researcher metadata considerations**

537 One goal of this survey, and the charge of the Researcher Communications Project
538 within Metadata 2020, was to identify levels of researcher knowledge about metadata for
539 publication, discovery of research, and data sets. The answers in the researcher survey reflect
540 a limited awareness on metadata in all of these areas (Researcher Survey Q6 and Q15).
541 However, when asked about how to evaluate different types of research outputs, responses
542 point to fields with rich metadata (Researcher Survey Q11 and Q12).

543 The other audiences surveyed maintain metadata for their own uses, which can leave
544 out the researchers' needs. For example, researchers might not receive adequate support from
545 publishers to increase their competency with creating and using metadata for data sets,
546 publications or other research projects (Publisher Survey Q3). Librarians, meanwhile, appear
547 to have many demands on their time in order to deal with incomplete metadata as provided to
548 them by publishers (Library Survey Q4 and Q5). They are often underutilized by researchers
549 as resources to help them fully leverage metadata for publications or data sets.

550 Answers in the repository manager survey reflect a mixed picture of metadata issues
551 in repositories. The number of repositories is growing and technologies for repository
552 administration are developing fast; however, repository metadata is the least standardized of
553 any metadata required by the stakeholder groups surveyed here.

554 In the cross-stakeholder analysis, the respondents' views on the most important
555 metadata fields reflect different priorities than expected by the Project. The respondents were
556 asked to select the most important metadata fields in a list of 28 fields. Of the top 11 fields
557 identified by the four stakeholder groups, publishers, researchers, and repository managers all
558 strongly endorsed the DOI and year and date of publication as the two most important pieces
559 of metadata, with the abstract and author ORCID being third and fourth most important
560 pieces. This means that two of the most important pieces of metadata are persistent
561 identifiers (PIDs). Librarians also identified the DOI and year and date of publication as the
562 two most important pieces of metadata, but not nearly with the same amount of consensus.
563 Moreover, librarians' third and fourth most important pieces of metadata were the
564 volume/issue number and the language of the content; abstracts and author ORCIDs were
565 fifth and sixth respectively. It is unclear exactly why there is a discrepancy about the value of
566 abstracts and ORCIDs between librarians and the other three groups but given librarians
567 strong need to educate researchers about metadata, it seems like there are opportunities for
568 librarians to better understand the needs of their researcher patrons.

569 **5.3 Next steps – future studies**

570 Having completed this survey on metadata with the different stakeholder groups, we
571 believe there are several avenues for further studies about improving metadata in the

572 scholarly communications life cycle. We must acknowledge the limitations of the
573 convenience sample of respondents who were predominantly from English speaking
574 countries and represent the organizations that control much in the scholarly communications
575 ecosphere. Future work would benefit from targeted recruitment from under-represented
576 areas of the world and stakeholders and should include questions about less common but
577 important items such as non-traditional works and indigenous knowledge.

578 ***5.3.1 Persona perspectives are important and multidimensional***

579 As work progressed with Metadata 2020's project groups, it became clear the original
580 stakeholder groups encompassed multiple roles. The work completed by other projects within
581 the Metadata 2020 effort resulted in identifying four types of personas--creators, custodians,
582 curators, and consumers--that cut across all of the stakeholder groups ([Metadata 2020](#)
583 [Personas, 2020](#)). These personas better encapsulate how metadata is handled in the scholarly
584 communications life cycle and these lenses can better situate how researchers interact with
585 metadata. Future work on metadata from the perspective of personas will align roles with
586 metadata life cycles that play a role for each stakeholder group.

587 ***5.3.2 Metadata workflows***

588 The survey reinforced Metadata 2020 workshop discussion about metadata
589 workflows. Metadata moves through various systems in complex and idiosyncratic ways, but
590 the various workflows have not been identified or studied in ways that can help researchers
591 learn more about where their metadata goes once it enters a platform or a publisher's website.
592 This survey did not address the receipt of metadata for further use, but this is another crucial
593 piece of understanding in metadata pipelines.

594 **5.3.3 Metadata as an essential part in applying the FAIR Principles**

595 The survey revealed more work can be done to provide a vision of an ecosystem that
596 supports the FAIR principles ([Wilkinson 2016](#)) and that also streamlines certain disjointed
597 and non-automated workflows across stakeholder groups. Researchers will benefit from
598 publishers, librarians, and repository managers having more interoperability in metadata.

599 **5.3.4 Specific metadata elements**

600 The survey includes a lot of data on which metadata elements are rated as important
601 by the groups, and many of these findings are interesting for further studies. ORCIDs, for
602 example, could be explored for different types of uses by researchers if added functionalities
603 could be added. The “Abstract” metadata element is also an interesting theme for further
604 study and the Initiative for Open Abstracts (I4OA) is already leading the way with expanding
605 the availability of abstracts.

606 **5.3.5 Increased standardization of metadata**

607 There may also be a need for the Journal Article Tagging Suite (JATS), which was
608 intentionally developed as a descriptive model, to be revisited in order to make JATS terms
609 more prescriptive ([Journal Article Tag Suite 2020](#)). This would enable content to be tagged
610 in a more consistent way, making it more consistent and predictable for improved machine-
611 readability.

612 **5.3.6 The importance of controlled vocabularies for metadata**

613 Controlled vocabularies have an impact on visibility and discoverability of researcher
614 outputs. This study focused less on controlled vocabularies and more on the schema, such as
615 Dublin Core, that use them. More work can be done to understand the perceived value of and

616 usage of controlled vocabularies, as well as examining tools for enriching research output
617 with controlled vocabularies and ontologies. We are aware of the ongoing evolvement of
618 tools and techniques for ontologies and controlled vocabularies, such as the SPAR
619 Ontologies ([Peroni 2018](#)).

620 *5.3.7 Streamlining metadata deposits for researchers*

621 Researchers are increasingly struggling with administrative demands associated with
622 creating metadata for funding applications, publications, and data sets and yet they are the
623 most familiar with the best way to describe these objects to support findability and use by
624 other researchers. More work is needed to see what types of partnerships researchers can
625 foster with data repositories and academic libraries to streamline metadata creation.
626 Additionally, as more researchers become aware of the FAIR Principles ([Wilkinson 2016](#))
627 and their utility, the practices of asking for new metadata during the publishing process
628 should be evaluated to increase ease of use and compliance. Further, only the researchers
629 mentioned bibliographic management tools such as Endnote, Refworks, Zotero and
630 Mendeley. There are opportunities to integrate future metadata components to enhance such
631 tools, one such opportunity is to use semantic web technologies to enrich relationships across
632 scholarly domains.

633 *5.3.8 Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) not specifically addressed in our survey*

634 While the use of PIDs continues to increase and the application of standards to
635 control their use across communities gains more acceptance, new opportunities continue to
636 arise. Some PIDs do have metadata embedded in them, for example, more work can be done
637 to enrich PIDs with more metadata.

638 **5.3.9 Semantic web technologies not addressed in the survey**

639 Massive opportunities exist to use metadata created in the publishing life cycle to
640 create semantic metadata. There is evidence that repository managers are the stakeholder
641 group most familiar with the metadata schema and encoding languages that facilitate
642 ontological metadata (JSON, RDF, Schema.org), but metadata is only beginning to be used
643 for these purposes in the research lifecycle. Researchers do not usually operate in this space,
644 meaning that education is the first step toward developing metadata intended for a semantic
645 web platform.

646 **Appendix. Supplementary Materials**

647 **A.1 Survey Methods and Summary Results**

648 **A.1.1 Description**

649 This document serves as the companion to this article. It represents an analyzed data
650 set of the raw data collected for the Metadata 2020 survey. The purpose of the data summary
651 is to draw attention to the unique responses of each stakeholder group. The authors of this
652 article jointly analyzed and developed this analysis. ([Kaiser 2021](#))

653 **A.1.2 Citation**

654 Kaiser K, Urberg M, Johnsson M, Kemp J, Meadows A, & Paglione L. (2021).
655 Metadata 2020 Metadata Usage Survey Methods and Results Summary (Version 0.1.0).
656 *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4666086>

657 **A.2 Survey Questions**

658 **A.2.1 Description**

659 This document records the finalized version of the survey that was distributed,
660 following IRB approval, to a broad number of communities. The questions were answered by
661 participants self-identifying as researchers, publishers, librarians, and repository managers.
662 The purpose of these questions was to assess how metadata is understood by stakeholders in
663 the scholarly communications life cycle. To the designers' best knowledge, no other survey
664 had previously attempted to analyze knowledge about, and perceptions of metadata
665 associated with publication. The survey was conceived as a primary output by the Metadata
666 2020 Researcher Communications Project and the survey instrument was developed with the
667 assistance of stakeholder groups active in Metadata 2020. ([Metadata 2020 Survey Questions](https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00133/1912221/qss_a_00133.pdf)
668 [2021](https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00133/1912221/qss_a_00133.pdf))

669 **A.2.2 Citation**

670 Metadata 2020, Kaiser K, Urberg M, Johnsson M, Kemp J, Meadows A, & Paglione
671 L. (2021). Metadata 2020 Metadata Usage Survey Questions (Version 0.1.0). *Zenodo*.
672 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4666192>

673 **A.3 Raw survey data**

674 **A.3.1 Description**

675 This document contains the excel spreadsheet with all of the raw, unanalyzed
676 responses to the Metadata 2020 Survey. Each stakeholder group is represented with its own
677 tab. In addition, one tab contains all of the responses, another the demographics for the
678 survey. The responses in these tabs may include incomplete responses. Two other tabs

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Quantitative Science Studies. Advance Publication. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00133

679 contain comparisons of how each stakeholder group has self-prioritized metadata fields and
680 metadata schema, which are discussed in this paper further. ([Paglione 2021](#))

681 *A.3.2 Citation*

682 Paglione L, Kaiser K, Urberg M, Johnsson M, Kemp J, Meadows A. (2021). Raw
683 Data: An International, Multi-Stakeholder Survey about Metadata Awareness, Knowledge,
684 and Use in Scholarly Communications [Excel spreadsheet]. Location:
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761

762 **Acknowledgements**

763 The authors would like to thank all respondents to the survey, as well as the project
764 teams for Metadata 2020 who helped to develop and refine the question sets. We are also
765 grateful to Rachael Lammey of Crossref for generating the online survey forms. And, finally,
766 many thanks to the Metadata 2020 instigators and maintainers who have supported this
767 project, including Metadata 2020's project managers Clare Dean and Laura Paglione.

768 **Competing interests**

769 Disclosures: The authors have no conflicts of interest to report.

Kaiser, K.A., Urberg, M., Johnsson, M., Kemp, J., Meadows, A., Paglione, L. (2021) An International, Multi- Stakeholder Survey about Metadata Awareness, Knowledge and Use in Scholarly Communications. Quantitative Science Studies. Advance Publication. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00133 42

770

Data Availability

771

The data used in the study leading to this paper are available with supporting

772

materials to facilitate their use. A list of these materials can be found in the Appendix.

773

(Paglione 2021)